

Quantum Average Momentum Compared with Classical Statistical Pressure Part IV Interference in Terms of Probabilistic Impulses

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In Part III we considered the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ as consisting of two parts $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ treated as two different dimensions. We also argued that each, is a probability distribution in space and so associated with an internal force. One may notice that $\exp(ipx)$ does not contain time, but still predicts the direction of motion. Given that one cannot consider $x(t)$ within a wavelength \hbar/p even though on average the particle moves as $x=p/m t$, there is no real sense of time within a wavelength. Extending this idea, one repeats $\cos(px)$ humps. Given that the particle is moving, one must somehow juxtapose two spatial probability densities. The derivative of the distribution is proportional to average momentum and so one may see the notion of action-reaction occurring between $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and within $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ accounting for the sign changes with x . We argue that $d/dx \cos(px)$ regions which change sign imply that the impulse direction changes.

Furthermore, $\cos(px)$ has regions near the endpoints of the wavelength which have very low values (close to zero) which is fine if one has two juxtapositioned distributions. If, however, one creates a single particle bound state, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$ (a specific parity) give the appearance of a cancelation leaving the impression of $2\cos(px)$ i.e a single “static” distribution. This occurs because there is no internal time in the picture and so p and $-p$ probabilities add. The so-called canceled pieces have not really disappeared. as will be argued, they simply do not contribute to an average impulse which is what experiments apparently detect. Thus “negative” quantum probability is linked to impulse in the opposite direction, we argue. Thus interference is really linked to the notion of probabilistic impulses i.e. $p \exp(ipx)$ even though $\exp(ipx)$ is used as a kind of probability.

$\exp(ipx)$ contains internal action-reaction impulse hits which have experimental consequences as we argue is shown in a reflection/refraction problem, but are also linked with impulse hits associated with p . Thus there are two sets of forces to deal with. This, we argue, explains why one writes the energy conservation equation $AA/c_1=BB/c_1+CC/c_2$ for reflection/refraction where A,B,C represent the incident, reflected and refracted rays and AA simply shows that intensity/flux is positive as two equations: $A+B=C$ and $A_p - pB = p_2C$ with $E=pc$. The two equations,, needed to solve for B,C in terms of A ,, describe the internal force in $\exp(ipx)$ and the probabilistic impulse $p \exp(ipx)$.

For a single particle bound state, one considers a linear combination of free particle states indicating that impulse hits represent the underlying physics. Given the apparent spatial invariance of a free particle $\exp(ipx)$, one may wonder how a kinetic energy profile appears. We argue that different p values yield different peak points for maximum impulse hits and these are out of synch leading to a spatial distribution of $KE(x)$ or $d/dx KE(x)$ which is equivalent to $-dV/dx = \text{Force}$ where $V(x)$ is the potential.

Single Particle Wavefunction

A classical particle with constant p moves as $x=p/m t$. A quantum free particle such as an electron also moves on average in the same way. In particular, the quantum wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ depends on $p= m_0 v$ (nonrelativistically) and $x=vt$. This has the appearance of a contradiction because a particle, it seems, cannot be moving as $x=p/m t$ and at the same time be linked to two spatial probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, treated as two dimensions. There is no probability in $x=p/m t$.

We argue that externally there is a clock and that the particle moves as $x=p/m t$, but internally $\exp(ipx)$ implies no time. $\exp(-Et)$ is linked to a frequency, but does not appear in time-independent analysis using $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$, however, must still indicate the direction of motion, even if there is no internal time. Thus there are two “dimensions”, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. This two dimensions occur together (separated by “ i ”) because if there is a probability distribution $\cos(px)$ within a wavelength \hbar/p , the particle is simultaneously moving and should also have a probability to be at an x in the translated wavelength, hence $\cos(px) + i\sin(px)$. The modulus of this yields 1 indicating that all x points have the same weight as should be the case for constant p .

The presence of a wavelength, implied by $\exp(ipx)$, which is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$ i.e. of the spatial generator, indicates that an internal ruler grating is established, but this forces a spatial distribution which implies internal force in a sense because something is forcing one x point to be preferred over the other. Overall no x is preferred, so the internal force in $\cos(px)$ must be “balanced” by the internal force in $\sin(px)$ (in the second dimension). If one draws $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ graphs starting from $x=0$, one may see qualitatively the action-reaction of the slopes.

A main point we wish to make is the form $\exp(ipx)$ seems to imply to sets of “force” scenarios:

- A) There seems to exist an internal force scenario associated with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ accounting for the existence of these distributions even though each x should have the same weight for constant motion. The shape of the distributions allow for the modulus to achieve a constant $\text{Probability}(x)$. Thus we argue for an internal action-reaction. This is important because it governs the behaviour of average impulse hits by p the particle momentum.
- B) A quantum particle with momentum p delivers an impulse of $2p$ (if it bounces back with p) anywhere within the wavelength even though it has different probabilities $\cos(px)$. It is, however, most likely for a hit to occur when $\cos(px)=1$. Thus we introduce the idea of a probabilistic impulse i.e. $p \exp(ipx)$. This governs quantum interactions. In general, $\exp(ipx)$ is used as a probability with p dropped, but we argue that the underlying physical notion is one of probabilistic impulses.

$\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ play the role of a kind of spatial probability which is not $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction i.e. $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. It is difficult to understand the notion of probability being negative i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ taking on negative values. If one thinks in terms of impulses as being the key physical notion, then $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are “mathematical”

square root flux type probabilities which serve to describe the physical impulse probability. Thus the probabilistic impulse is:

$$d/dx \cos(px) = -p \sin(px) \quad ((1))$$

If one multiplies by $E/\hbar = 1/\text{time} = p/\hbar$ one obtains a force. ((2))

Thus $\sin(px)$ being negative indicates that the probabilistic impulse is in the “opposite” direction.

We now wish to focus on an experimental scenario which shows the two forces (A) and (B) at work.

Reflection/Refraction of Light

Consider the problem of light moving in the positive x direction reflecting/refracting at a medium along the y axis at $x=0$. The probabilities for reflection and refraction are unknown. A given photon, however, retains its energy whether it reflects or refracts even though momentum and light speed c change according to $E=pc$. Considering a steady state system with intensity/flux, one may write conservation of energy as:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((3))$$

Here A,B,C describe the incident, reflected and refracted beam intensities and AA is used to indicate that intensity is strictly positive. In previous notes we argued that one has two unknowns B,C if A is given, but only one equation ((3)). To bypass this problem we suggested writing a difference of squares:

$$A+B=C \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad Ap - Bp = Cp^2 \quad ((4b))$$

In previous notes we spoke of a kind of continuity of square root fluxes (where A is a square root) flux and even described the overall form of this square root flux as $\exp(ipx)$. The positive and negative parts of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ allow for “cancellations” needed in ((4a)) if $n_1 < n_2$ where n is the index of refraction. In such a case, $B < 0$ so it may cancel part of A allowing the result to equal C. In addition, there are two equations ((4a)) and ((4b)) allowing one to solve for the two unknowns B,C in terms of A.

What, however, is the physical meaning of the two equations? We argue the two are linked to (A) and (B) given in the previous section. There is an internal action-reaction force in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ associated with constant p motion as argued in Part III. Such a force is physically real and so one may have cancellations of force as in Newtonian mechanics. In other words, B’s internal $\exp(ipx)$ forces partially cancel those of A giving the sense of a diminished overall beam $A+B$ represented in terms of internal forces.

Thus ((4a)) makes sense described in terms of this internal force, while speaking of a continuity of a square root flux is not really physical.

The second equation ((4b)) shows the consequence of the periodic internal action-reaction force on the probabilistic impulse $pA\exp(ipx)$. The impulse from hitting the particle is $2p$, but given the internal action-reaction being associated with the probability distribution $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, there is a probabilistic impulse. Thus two equations are needed to describe the two force schemes in the problem. This seems to be the reason for “taking the square root” to obtain two equations. The two equations describe the two force schemes existing, with one affecting the other. Thus this physical scenario allows for the solution of the two unknowns B,C.

Single Particle Quantum Bound State

We next consider the single particle quantum bound state. A main idea of this problem is that for a given parity, say $a(p)=a(-p)$, $a(p)\exp(ipx)+a(-p)\exp(-ipx) = 2 a(p) \cos(px)$. In other words one obtains a “static” spatial probability distribution instead of the dynamic probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. The cancellation, however, serves to describe probabilistic impulses felt. There is no real cancellation in the sense that $i\sin(px)$ and $-i\sin(px)$ are destroyed. If the particle is knocked out of the bound state its wavelength is $\exp(ipx)$. The $i \sin(px)$ is present. Thus we argue the “cancellation” describes what an experimentalist would detect. There is no time and the probabilistic impulses associated with $p \sin(px)$ and $-p \sin(-px)$ yield equal and opposite hits which gives the appearance of “no hit”. Thus, as argued in Part III, $W(x)$ which includes interference is a “freezing out” of dynamic parts which “seem” to cancel in order to create a “static” type of probability distribution which seems to exist in the sense that this is what an experiment would measure.

When describing a single particle quantum bound state, one uses an ensemble of free particle states $\exp(ipx)$ i.e $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This suggests impulses are the key physical idea. The impulses are linked to p and to the internal forces within $\exp(ipx)$ which creates spatial densities in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. As argued in the first section, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ being negative may be interpreted as a negative impulse being delivered (i.e. an impulse in the opposite direction of the positive case). Thus, ultimately one is concerned with impulses with $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ in the form of a conditional probability being a convenient math tool.

Given that one has an ensemble of $\exp(ipx)$ s which have a “kind of” spatial invariance, why does one find an average kinetic energy which $KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$ which has a specific spatial distribution which does not exhibit spatial invariance? We argue this is due to different $\exp(ipx)$ s representing different wavelengths \hbar/p . The peaks of various $\cos(px)$ differ and we argue these represent the locations of maximum probabilistic impulses. Thus one ultimately wishes to form a picture of the impulses. As a first step, one may consider the maximum impulse hit points. These occur at the peaks of $\cos(px)$, but $a(p)$ values determine weights. Furthermore different $\cos(px)$ s behave differently within different half wavelength regions. Consider $\cos(p_1x)$ and $\cos(p_2x)$. If $1 \frac{1}{3}$ half wavelengths of p_2 fit within a wavelength of p_1 , then at the end the first half wavelength of p_1 , p_2 is at the $\frac{1}{3}$ half wavelength point, but at the end of the next half wavelength region of p_1 , p_2 is at the $\frac{2}{3}$ wavelength point. As a result, interference (which describes probabilistic impulses) creates a “distribution” which is not spatially invariant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there are two sets of forces in a quantum problem. First, there is an internal action-reaction force within $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which constitute $\exp(ipx)$. The fact that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ both have positive and negative regions indicates the idea of action/reaction. Within a wavelength there is no notion of internal time. The particle has a spatial distribution to be at one x or another, but at the same time it is moving, so the “wavelength” is shifting so to speak and there is another probability distribution. Thus one needs to juxtapose the two as separate dimensions to indicate the direction of motion. The two, however, must also demonstrate that each x point has the same weight. Thus there is not only action-reaction within $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but between the two so that one has the appearance of smooth motion created by two dimensions representing accelerating motion i.e. a spatial distribution.

This spatial distribution represented by $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ affects a second probabilistic force in the problem due impulse created by the momentum p . Any specific impulse with a quantum particle with momentum p is given by $2p$, but there is a probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$ has a peak at $\cos(px)=1$ so the probabilistic impulse is the greatest there. Thus there is the notion of a probabilistic impulse $2p \exp(ipx)$.

In a single particle quantum bound state, with $a(p)=a(-p)$ i.e. a specific parity, $a(p)\exp(ipx)+a(-p)\exp(-ipx) = 2a(p) \cos(px)$. Thus there is the appearance of a cancellation of probability, but it does not really disappear, it is just linked to equal and opposite probabilistic impulses which are not picked up in an experiment, it seems. Thus one has the appearance of a static $2a(p)\cos(px)$. $\cos(px)$ may take positive and negative values which seems unusual if it is thought of as a probability (or square root flux probability), but in terms of probabilistic impulses there is no issue. $\cos(px)$ affects the probabilistic impulse of p and a negative sign means an impulse in the opposite direction. Thus we suggest one should consider a quantum state problem in terms of impulses. The form $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ also indicates this. The spatial distribution of $KE(x)$ (linked to $V(x_0)$) simply indicates that different peak values of $\cos(px)$ for different p values occur at different places in such a manner that probabilistic impulses, which add as in Newtonian mechanics, do not yield a spatially invariant result. This is the idea of interference we argue.

We finally note that the two kind of forces, the internal action-reaction within $\exp(ipx)$, and the probabilistic impulse of $p\exp(ipx)$ explain physically why a reflection/refraction experiment may be described by $A+B=C$ and $Ap-pB=p^2C$ where $AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2$ and $E=pc$ where AA, BB, CC are the intensities of the incident, reflected and refracted beams.